

Magnetic activity cycles in the open cluster NGC 6811?

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Abstract

The sun shows a magnetic activity cycle related to the occurrence of spots on its surface with a strong periodicity of 11 years. With the advent of space missions like CoRoT and *Kepler*, astronomers began to try and find ways to associate the photometric variability of the star with its intrinsic magnetic activity. Photometric proxies for activity appear to be correlated with the chromospheric \mathcal{S} index and p-modes from asteroseismology. In order to investigate the existence and properties of magnetic cycles in a narrow range of fundamental parameters, we studied solar-type stars in the intermediate-age open cluster NGC 6811. We searched our sample for cycle-like periodicities and in each case classified the variability as either cyclic, multicyclic, flat or acyclic. We checked the usual correlations between P_{cyc} , P_{rot} and Rossby number and we find a high degree of dispersion among them, which casts doubt on the existence of the Active branch. We introduce theoretical questions about what determines the activity cycle period and whether there is some sort of fundamental difference between cyclic and acyclic stars. The comparison between stars with the same mass, age and chemistry suggests that neither of these properties is truly decisive.

1 Introduction

Magnetic activity cycles, first observed in the periodic fluctuations of the solar spot number, have since been found in other stars by means of spectroscopic indicators of intrinsic activity, such as R'_{HK} and the \mathcal{S} index. Variations in photometric signals have shown a direct correspondence to the signatures of stellar activity (e.g., García *et al.*, 2010).

In this work we search for patterns among these cyclic signals in solar type stars from NGC 6811. This was one of the four clusters observed by the *Kepler* Cluster Study and its metallicity is very similar to solar. This means that our sample will consist of young sun-like objects, presumably with magnetic processes very much alike our own sun but a lot more active. We also expect the activity cycles to be shorter than solar, assuming that $\omega_{\text{cyc}} \propto \Omega$ is approximately valid (Böhm-Vitense, 2007), which means it can be detected in the 4 year long time series available in long cadence from *Kepler*.

2 Sample description

We cross-matched the stars from the NASA Exoplanet Archive to *Gaia* DR2 (GDR2) within a search radius of 1 arc-second and removed every object with negative or poorly determined parallaxes ($\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi} \leq 5$).

We applied distance and proper motion filters based on the astrometric solutions of GDR2 as detailed in Table 1. The main astrophysical properties of the cluster were thoroughly studied in Sandquist *et al.* (2016) and our sample of candidate members from *Gaia* astrometry is well fit to a PARSEC isochrone with a total metal content $Z = 0.0170$ and the accepted age of 1.0 Gyr.

We proceeded to select stars within $0.95 \leq M/M_{\odot} \leq 1.05$ according to the *Kepler* Stellar Properties Catalogue (KSPC DR25), leaving us with a final sample of 36 stars. We used the long cadence light curves from *Kepler* to determine the P_{rot} of each one of them using both generalized Lomb-Scargle pe-

riodograms (GLS) and the Auto-Correlation Function (ACF). We plot in Figure 1 these rotation rates as a function of *Gaia* color over the 70 FGK stars from Meibom *et al.* (2011), which define the tight sequence corresponding to the gyrochronology profile of the 1.0 Gyr cluster.

3 Results

We calculated the S_{ph} as the standard deviation of a segment of the light curve as described in Mathur *et al.* (2014). The segments had a window length of $k \times P_{\text{rot}}$, with $k = 3$ and $k = 5$. The highest peak and the False Alarm Probability (FAP) were calculated for each periodogram of the time series formed by consecutive S_{ph} measurements and, if the FAP was lower than 5% for both values of k , it was classified as a “statistically significant cycle”; if it was lower than 5% only for the case $k = 3$, it was classified as a “sampling dependent cycle”.

Among our sample of 36 stars, we identified 7 which were acyclic (random variations of S_{ph}), 16 which were flat (negligible variation of S_{ph}), 13 were cyclic (either statistically significant or sampling dependent) and one of those showed clear multicyclic behavior (two significant frequency components). Some examples of each case can be seen in Figure 2.

Noyes *et al.* (1984) propose an empirical cubic fit for the

Table 1: Membership astrometric criteria used in this study.

Parameter	Literature values	Filter
α (deg)	294.3208	294.3 ± 0.7
δ (deg)	46.3883	46.4 ± 0.5
d (pc)	995 to 1150	1100 ± 200
μ_{α} (mas/yr)	-4.95	-4.5 ± 1.5
μ_{δ} (mas/yr)	-7.78	-8.5 ± 1.5

Figure 1: The observed color–period diagram in *Gaia* photometry for sun-like stars in NGC 6811 over the clear I-type sequence of FGK stars studied in Meibom *et al.* (2011). Vertical lines indicate the limits between minimum and maximum P_{rot} found by different methods.

convective turnover time τ_c as a function of $(B - V)$ color which closely matches the theoretical curve for $\alpha \sim 2$. We used this fit together with equations by Jester *et al.* (2005) to transform the $(g-r)_{\text{KIC}}$ colors from the *Kepler* Input Catalog (KIC) to $(B - V)$ color and from that derive τ_c .

We then applied the definition of the Rossby number $R_o = P_{\text{rot}}/4\pi\tau_c$ to our observed rotation periods and derived turnover times to plot the usual diagram $P_{\text{rot}}/P_{\text{cyc}}$ versus $1/R_o$ (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

A first important aspect to be discussed concerns the astrophysical nature of the long-term photometric variability measured by this method. Salabert *et al.* (2016) argue, after studying the light curves of 18 seismic solar analogue stars together with measurements from HERMES, that the S_{ph} as a photometric proxy for activity is strongly correlated with the chromospheric S index and the p-modes from asteroseismology. That being said, some long-term signal variability is known to be introduced by the corrections performed in the light curves by the Pre-search Data Conditioning (PDC) pipeline.

Whatever the intrinsic source of this kind of variability turns out to be, it should be expected that, given the same signal processing, this coeval collection of very similar stars in terms of mass and metallicity originate the same sort of general behaviour, which is clearly not the case here. If these cycle-like periodicities truly represent the dynamo processes happening in stellar interiors, then one possible explanation would be the chaotic nature of the dynamic system, where non-linearities in the internal magnetic processes propagate small deviations in the initial parameters to significant scattering in the output observed.

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Figure 2: Different types of cyclic behavior found among our sample.

Figure 3: Correlation between $P_{\text{rot}}/P_{\text{cyc}}$ and R_o , with Active (A) and Inactive (I) branches as in Saar & Brandenburg (1999). The area of the rectangles reflect the uncertainties.

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